

Ba'zi 3d-metallarning 2,6-diaminopiridin bilan kompleks birikmalari sintezi va ularning biologik faolligi

¹Nazarov Y. E.,

²Turayev X.X.,

³O'rolova D.O'.

¹Termiz davlat universiteti, k.f.f.d.

²Termiz davlat universiteti, k.f.d., prof.

³Termiz davlat universiteti talabasi.

E-mail: nazarovy714@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. 2,6-diaminopiridin ligandining kompleks birikmalarni o'rganish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ular biologik faol bo'lganligi uchun keng qo'llaniladi. Ayniqsa bu borada 3d-metall komplekslari dori ta'sirini samarali ortirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Metall ionining tabiati, shuningdek ligand turi tufayli farmako logik faoliyatda muhim ahamiyatga ega muhim ahamiyatga ega turli metallar va ligandlar har xil biologik xususiyatga ega. Jumladan karboksilat guruhi tutgan ligand (piridindikarbon, aminopiridinkarbon kislota, glutamat, aspartat,) va tufayli qiziqarli soha bo'lib kelgan. Ikki yoki undan ortiq karboksilik guruhlarning turli burchaklardagi bog'lanishi 1D (uzun zanjir), 2D (varaqa) yoki 3D (qafas) tuzilishini shakllantirishga imkon beradi. Ushbu muammolarni oldini olish uchun d metall ioni va ularning komplekslarini tegishli biologik faollik uchun ishlatishimiz mumkin. Ushbu preparatlarda d metall ionidan foydalanish zaharli ta'sirni osongina kamaytirishi va dori-darmonlarni tanadan samarali va tezroq olib tashlash imkonini beradi. So'nggi yillarda DNK molekulyar zondlari va kimyoterapevtiklar sohasida d metall komplekslarini o'rganuvchi tadqiqotlar tufayli juda muhim bo'ldi. 2,6-diaminopiridin metall hamda molekulyar komplekslarini olishni, ularning kristall tuzilishi bilan birgalikda fizik – kimyoviy hamda biologik xususiyatlarini tadqiq qilishni o'z oldimizga maqsad qildik. **Kalit so'zlar.** 2,6-diaminopiridin, kompleks birikma, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonasae rugi nosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Candida albicans*.

Kirish. Hozirgi kunda organik-noorganik gibrid birikmalarning sintezi ilmiy sohalarda keng e'tiborni tortdi, chunki ular g'ayrioddiy yangi xususiyatlar va ko'p funksiyali xarakterga egadir [1]. Shuning uchun ular nafaqat fundamental tadqiqotlarning yangi sohalasi ifodalaydi, balki, optika, qattiq elektrolitlar, kataliz, biomateriallar kabi turli sohalarda ko'plab yangi tadqiqotlarda obyekt hisoblanadi. [2,3]. Bundan tashqari, bu

kompleks birikmalar sohasidagi tadqiqotlar ularning maxsus magnit va elektron xususiyatlari tufayli katta ahamiyatga ega materiallarni tayyorlashga olib keladi va biologik faoldir [4,5]. Ayniqsa, 2,6-diaminopiridin kabi organik materiallar og'riq qoldiruvchi dori-darmonlarni sintez qilish uchun farmatsevtik vosita sifatida ahamiyatlidir [6]. Boshqa tomondan, galogenli gibrud birikmalarni o'z ichiga olgan noorganik materiallar aniq afzalliklarga ega. Ushbu afzalliklarga yaxshi elektr harakatchanligi, magnit xususiyatlar va termik barqarorlik [7,8], ayniqsa kobalt (II) komplekslarida kuzatiladi. Co^{2+} birikmalari qiziqarli optik xossalari tufayli magnit va yarim o'tkazuvchan materiallarni yaratish va arzon elektron qurilmalarni yaratish uchin ajayib boshlang'ich nuqta bo'ldi [9]. Shu bilan birga, oraliq metallarning galogenid birikmalari bo'yicha olibborilayotgan ba'zi tadqiqotlar bilan birgalikda organik-noorganik materiallarning kristall tuzilishi va fizik xususiyatlari o'rganilgan [10].

Zn (II)ning 2,6-DAPY kompleks birikmasi sintezi

Rux (II)sulfat kristallogidratidan $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 0.1435 gr (0.5 mmol), 0.02725 gr (0.25 mmol) 2,6-DAPYni tegishli suv va etil spirtida eritib, 2;1 nisbatdagi eritmalari tayyorlandi. So'ngra magnitli aralashtirgich yordamida 60°C da 30 minut davomida intensiv aralashtirildi. Eritma xona haroratida qoldirildi. Natijada 14 kundan so'ng idish tubida rangsiz kompleks birikma kristali o'sganligi kuzatildi. RTT analizi uchun yaroqli kristallar ajratilib, tekshirilganda $2[\text{Zn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6](2,6\text{-DAPY})(\text{SO}_4)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ tarkibli ekanligi aniqlandi. Unumi 85 % $2[\text{Zn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6](2,6\text{-DAPY})(\text{SO}_4)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ $\text{Zn}_2\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{64}\text{O}_{28}\text{N}_6\text{S}_4$ ($M_r = 974.152$ g/mol) C H N S O tahlili nazariy jihatdan: C 12.31, H 6.62, N 8.62, S 12.31, O 45.66 % ni ko'rsatdi: ma'lum bo'ldiki C 12.08, H 6.34, N 8.45, S 12,12, O 45.35%. Reaksiya tenglamasi quyidagicha (1-reaksiya).

1-rasm. $2[\text{Zn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6](2,6\text{-DAPY})_2(\text{SO}_4)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ kompleksining molekulyar tuzilishi

Olingan kompleks birikmaning biologik faolligi. Olingan yangi 2,6-DAPY komplekslarining test shtammlarga nisbatan faolligi dastlabki ligand bilan taqqoslash asosida o'rganildi. Tadqiqot uchun olingan namunalar barchasi (namunalar konsentratsiyasi 0.03 mkm/mol) sinov test shtammlarga nisbatan turli xil faollikni ko'rsatdi: *Staphylococcus aureus* uchun o'sishning ingiberlash zonasi 13 mm dan 28 mm gacha, *Candida albicans* uchun 15 dan 25 mm gacha. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* uchun 15 dan 31 mm gacha va *Escherichia coli* uchun 12 dan 36 mm gacha, *Bacillus subtilis* da bu ko'rsatgich 16 dan 39 mm gacha bakteritsid faolligi kuzatildi (1-jadval).

1-jadval

Ligand ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}_3$) va uning kompleks birikmalarining mikroblarga qarshi faolligi (3-5 kun)

Namuna	Antogonistik faollik d (o'sishini ingibirlash zonasi), mm				
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Pseudomona sae rugi nosa</i>	<i>Staphyloccus aureus</i>	<i>Candida albicans</i>
0 2,6-DAPY	16	12	15	13	15
1 $[\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6](2,6\text{-DAPY})_2(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	24	36	31	26	25
2 $[\text{Mn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6](2,6\text{-DAPY})_2(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	20	14	23	17	16

	$(\text{DAPY})_2(\text{SO}_4)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$					
3	$[\text{Zn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6](2,6\text{-DAPY})_2(\text{SO}_4)_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	39	25	19	28	22

Bacillus subtilis

Escherichia coli

2-rasm. Olingan komplekslarning test shtammlarga antagonistik faolligi

Xulosa. 2,6-diaminopiridin (2,6-DAPY) ning $[\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6](2,6\text{-DAPY})_2(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$, $[\text{Mn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6](2,6\text{-DAPY})_2(\text{SO}_4)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$, $[\text{Zn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6](2,6\text{-DAPY})_2(\text{SO}_4)_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ kompleks birikmalari olinib, ularning monokristallari o'stirildi. Ularning tarkibi RTT bilan isbotlandi. Tegishli (CCDC) depozit nomerlari olindi. Ularning antogonistik faollik d (o'sishini ingibirlash zonasi) aniqlash orqali biologik faolligi yuqori ekanligi aniqlandi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati.

1. Azouzi K. et al. Synthesis, structure and Hirshfeld surface analysis, vibrational and DFT investigation of (4-pyridine carboxylic acid) tetrachlorocuprate (II) monohydrate //Bulletin of Materials Science. – 2017. – T. 40. – C. 289-299.
2. Mhadhbi N., Naili H., Jarraya K. Structural characterization and physicochemical features of a new arsenate salt templated by mono and di-protonated 4-aminopyridine cations: $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{N}_2)(\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)[\text{AsO}_4] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ //Physica E: Low-dimensional Systems and Nanostructures. – 2017. – T. 87. – C. 171-177.
3. Pardo R., Zayat M., Levy D. Photochromic organic–inorganic hybrid materials

//Chemical Society Reviews. – 2011. – T. 40. – №. 2. – C. 672-687.

4. Sanchez C. et al. Applications of advanced hybrid organic–inorganic nanomaterials: from laboratory to market //Chemical Society Reviews. – 2011. – T. 40. – №. 2. – C. 696-753.

5. R.V. Singh, K. Sharma, M. Jain, Platinum (II) complexes of heterocyclic ligands of biological importance, Heterocycl. Commun. 10 (2004) 319e323. <https://doi.org/10.1515/hc.2004.10.4-5.319>.

6. Nasr M. B. et al. Synthesis, crystal structure, magnetic properties and second harmonic generation of a new noncentrosymmetric coordination compound: Triaqua (4-amino-6-methoxypyrimidine) cuprate (II) sulfate //Chinese Chemical Letters. – 2016. – T. 27. – №. 6. – C. 896-900.

7. Mirzaei M. et al. Syntheses, crystal, molecular structures, and solution studies of Cu (II), Co (II), and Zn (II) coordination compounds containing pyridine-2, 6-dicarboxylic acid and 1, 4-pyrazine-2, 3-dicarboxylic acid: comparative computational studies of Cu (II) and Zn (II) complexes //Structural Chemistry. – 2011. – T. 22. – C. 1365-1377.

8. Nazarov Y.E., Turaev Kh.Kh., Suyunov J.R., Ibragimov B.T., Alimnazarov B.Kh., Ashurov J.M. 8-Hydroxyquinolinium trichlorido(pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid- $\kappa^3\text{O,N,O}'$)copper(II) dihydrate Acta Crystallographica Section E: Crystallographic Communications, 2024, 80(10), c 1049–1053 <https://doi.org/10.1107/S2056989024009186>

9. Khayit Kh. Turaev, Yusufjon E. Nazarov, Abdukadir Kh. Tashkulov, Sherzod A. Kasimov, Bekmurod Kh. Alimnazarov, Jamshid M. Ashurov, Aziz B. Ibragimov, Takashiro Akitsu, Changkun Xia, Abul Monsur Showkot Hossain. Synthesis of mononuclear Ni (II) and binuclear Cu (II) complexes from pyridine-2, crystal structure and Hirshfeld surface analysis, 6-dicarboxylic acid with monotholenamine and hydrochloric acid solution //Structural Chemistry. – 2025. – C. 1-13 <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11224-025-02468-9>

10. Yusufjon E. Nazarov, Khayit Kh. Turaev, Sherzod A. Kasimov, Jamshid M. Ashurov, Alisher G. Eshimbetov, Aziz B. Ibragimov, Abror K. Nomozov, Changkun Xia, Abul Monsur Showkot Hossain Synthesis, crystal structures, DFT calculations, and hirshfeld surface analysis of tris(quinolin-8-olato- $\kappa^2\text{N,O}$)cobalt(III) acetic acid monosolvate and Bis(μ -quinolin-8-olato- $\kappa^2\text{N,O}$)diaquabis(nitrato- $\kappa^2\text{O,O}'$)dinickel(II) complexes Journal of Molecular Structure 1359 (2026) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2026.145469>